

Grain size analysis test

JJ0101a

Purpose		Grain size			Specimens		soil			
Date		2021.5.12								
test basis		JTG E40-2007								
equipment		drying case(TG-07); electronic balance(TG-10); Soil standard sieve(TG-11)。								
Cc		13.0			Cu			1.1		
Rough screening analysis					Fine screening analysis					
aperture (mm)	Quantifying the quality of retained soil (g)	Cumulative sieve soil quality (g)	Soil mass less than this aperture (g)	Percentage of soil mass less than that aperture (%)	aperture (mm)	Quantifying the quality of retained soil (g)	Cumulative sieve soil quality (g)	Soil mass less than this aperture (g)	Percentage of soil mass less than that aperture (%)	Percentage of total soil quality (%)
75					2	2.11		827.28		
60					1	12.88		814.40		
40					0.5	3.12		811.28		
20					0.25	5.27		806.01		
10					0.075	29.02		776.99	0.9368	
5			829.39							

